

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PASSIVE VOLTAGE SNUBBERS TO ATTENUATE THE EFFECTS OF LEAKAGE INDUCTANCE IN A QUASI-Y-SOURCE DC-DC CONVERTER

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Abstract

The use of renewable energy sources, especially photovoltaic, generated the need to develop new power converters with the ability to operate in a wide range of voltages with higher levels of flexibility, efficiency, and voltage gain. In this scenario, the converters based on impedance source networks of Quasi-Y (QSY) type, satisfy these requirements, having the feature of continuous input current, suitable for use in applications involving renewable energy sources. However, converters based on impedance source networks with magnetic coupling as a QSY type, have the inherent characteristic of producing large voltage efforts across the power switches during the converter operation, due to the existence of leakage inductance in the coupled inductors. Hence, the development of dampening circuits, such as passive voltage snubbers, is essential to allow the safe operation and protection of the power switch. This paper presents the study of three different types of passive voltage-dampening snubbers (RC, RCD, and LCD) applied in a QSY DC-DC converter, to attenuate the unwanted effects of leakage inductance. The design methods of the damping circuits applied to the QSY DC-DC converter are presented and the evaluation of the operation is carried out through computer simulations. The proposed design equations for the RCD and LCD snubbers proved to be effective through the simulation results, demonstrating their effectiveness. Among the three damping circuits evaluated, the LCD type showed better results, reducing the voltage stress across the power switch by 30% and increasing the efficiency of the converter, these results are promising and may allow the use of QSY converters in renewable energy applications.

Keywords: Quasi-Y DC-DC converter; leakage inductance, voltage snubber.

Introduction

Converters based on impedance networks, particularly the source-Y class, have shown promise for DC-AC and DC-DC power conversion in various applications related to renewable energy and motor drives, and many others. These converters have the advantage of the ability to operate in buck-boost mode employing a single stage composed of few components and more flexibility in voltage gains (Forouzesh, Abdelhakim, Siwakoti, & Blaabjerg, 2018).

However, the presence of magnetically coupled inductors and their respective dispersion inductances that compose the source impedance network Y, cause excessive voltage stress during switching, which can cause irreversible damage to the power switches. Therefore, impedance network type converters require the use of voltage damping circuits to absorb the energy of the leakage inductances and can

recover the energy to the circuit in a regeneration way, increasing the performance of the converter or just dissipating the energy of the voltage surge (Ahmadzadeh, Markadeh, & Blaabjerg, 2017).

In dissipative snubber, the stored energy is normally dissipated in a resistor, while regenerative snubber has components such as inductors and diodes that allow the stored energy to be returned to the input stage of the converter (García-Caraveo, Ángel Soto, & Bañuelos-Sánchez, 2010).

Among the dissipative passive snubber, the two most common are the resistor, capacitor (RC) and resistor, capacitor, diode (RCD), both of which dissipate all the stored leakage energy into the resistor, reducing the efficiency of the converter. A more efficient alternative is the LCD non-dissipative passive snubber, consisting of an inductor, a capacitor, and two diodes, which can return part of the absorbed energy back to the circuit input, thus becoming more efficient than the RC and RCD snubbers (Alganidi, 2017).

The RC, RCD, and LCD snubbers are widely discussed in several works of literature, however, their application in the Quasi-Y impedance source DC converter needs to be further explored since the addition of the snubbers changes the dynamic behavior of the converter. Intending to contribute to existing gaps in the state of knowledge of the application of damping circuits in converters based on impedance networks with magnetic coupling, this paper uses the knowledge already consolidated in the literature on RC, RCD, and LCD snubbers and presents the equations and procedures for determining the parameters of the snubbers for operation with the Quasi-Y converter. To this end, the design equations of each snubber are presented and using computer simulation using the PSIM software, the behavior and efficiency of the converter with and without the snubber are evaluated.

Source Y Impedance Network Based Converter

The converters based on impedance networks have great versatility offering operation as a step-down and step-up converter with great voltage increase capacity and can be used in DC-DC and DC-AC converters. The search for operational improvements concerning gains, minimization of effort, and cost have fostered the development of different types of impedance network topologies, such as T-source, Z-source, and Y-source, among others.

DC-DC Converter Quasi-Y Source

Among the impedance networks, the Quasi-Y Source type has been emphasized, which has the characteristic of continuous input current, suitable for use in applications involving renewable energy sources, such as solar or fuel cells. It is composed of 3 coupled inductors $N_1:N_2:N_3$ and an input inductor L_{in} that is associated with capacitor C_2 , prevents the saturation of the core of the coupled inductors, presenting two stages of operation, given by the conditions of the switch S_w (Santos & Gonçalves, 2021).

In the first stage, called shoot-through, the S_w switch is conducting, and the load is powered by the capacitor C_o . In the second stage, called non-shoot-through, the SW switch is blocked and the energy stored in the inductors recharges the capacitor C_o . Voltage stresses occur on the S_w switch, during the transition process between stages, due to the existence of magnetic elements with coupled cores, and their respective leakage inductances, represented in Figure 1, by the inductor L_k , which is the equivalent leakage inductance of the coupled inductors $N_1:N_2:N_3$, seen from the primary N_1 .

The presence of leakage inductance in the coupled inductors is an inherent characteristic of impedance networks, associated with the construction of the inductors, and difficult to eliminate, because in practice there will always be magnetic field lines of an inductor that are not coupled to the field lines of the other inductors (Erickson & Maksimović, 2020). The energy stored in these non-coupled field lines is dispersed in the transition period between the shoot-through and non-shoot-through modes, generating a surge in VSW and changing the behavior of the IN1 current, which delays a long time to reverse its direction, delaying the start of the non-shoot-through period, represented in Figure 2.

The energy stored in the dispersion inductance L_k is defined approximately by equation (1), where I_{lk} is equivalent to the current I_{N1} at the final instant of the shoot-through period.

$$\varepsilon_{lk} = \frac{1}{2} L_k I_{lk}^2 \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 shows an example of the behavior of the waveforms of the voltage and current on the S_W switch and the input currents I_{In} and I_{N1} . The resonance in the voltage V_{SW} is caused by the leakage inductance and the parasitic capacitances of the circuit.

Figure 1 - Quasi-Y DC source converter diagram (a), shoot-through mode (b), non-shoot-through mode (c)

Figure 2 - Quasi-Y DC-DC converter waveform operating without voltage snubber

The inherent behavior of the DC-DC converter Quasi-Y source related to the voltage stresses in the switching processes represents a very prejudicial aspect for the semiconductor switch, which together with the consequent resonance process, can make the commercial application inviable. Thus, the use of voltage snubbers circuits in this class of converters can contribute to the solution of these limitations, making the application viable, and still allowing the use of components with lower voltage specifications.

Voltage Snubber

To mitigate the high stresses observed in S_W , auxiliary circuits called snubbers can be used. In this paper, three passive-type voltage snubbers will be presented.

RC Voltage Snubber

Dissipative RC snubbers are widely used in various converter applications to mitigate resonance effects in switched circuits and are relatively simple to design and inexpensive to build. However, the high-power dissipation limits their use in low-power converters.

Figure 3 - Schematic diagram of Quasi-Y DC source converter with RC Snubber

Figure 3 shows the schematic diagram of the DC-DC converter Quasi-Y source considering the use of an RC snubber. When developing the design of this type of damper it is important to perform the sizing of R_S and C_S to obtain a proper balance between the required damping factor and the acceptable limit of thermal dissipation. Knowing the resonant frequency of the S_W switch and the value of the dispersion inductance L_{lk} measured at this same frequency, it is possible to calculate the characteristic impedance Z of the resonant circuit, using equation (2). A good starting rule is to consider the resistor value R_S equal to the characteristic impedance value Z (Ridley, 2005).

$$R_S = Z = 2\pi f_r L_{lk} \tag{2}$$

After defining the value of the resistor R_S , the next step is to calculate the value of the capacitor C_S , and a good starting rule is to consider that the capacitor C_S has a capacitive reactance equal to the resistance R_S , using equation (3).

$$C_S = \frac{1}{2\pi f_r R_S} \tag{3}$$

Considering that the resistor R_S dissipates energy during the charge and discharge of the capacitor C_S and knowing the values of the capacitor C_S , the voltage on the switch V_{SW} and the switching frequency f_{SW} , it is possible to estimate the energy dissipated in the snubber using equation (4).

$$\epsilon_S = C_S V_{SW}^2 f_{SW} \tag{4}$$

RCD Voltage Snubber

The RCD snubber is composed of 3 components: resistor, capacitor, and diode. This arrangement is widely used, due to its low cost and robustness characteristics, presenting good results in the function of absorbing the voltage stresses on the semiconductor switches and limiting the maximum overvoltage

value. However, the fact that it dissipates the absorbed energy, limits its use for small power (Finney, Williams, & Green, 1996).

Figure 4 presents the schematic diagram of the Quasi-Y DC-DC converter taking the operating principle of the RCD snubber is simple, starting at the instant the switch is switched to lock and the energy stored in the coupled inductors, flows through the diode D_S to the capacitor C_S that stores this energy, which in turn will be dissipated in the resistor R_S before the start of the next cycle.

Figure 4 - Schematic diagram of Quasi-Y DC source converter with RC Snubber

To design the RCD snubber, the methodology, consists in measuring the value of the leakage inductance L_{lk} , at the switching frequency of the converter, adopting the values of $\Delta V_{sw_average}$ and ΔV_{sw_stress} that are desired to be obtained, and the values of the peak current I_p and ΔV_{sw_spike} of the converter without the snubber and the duration time of the shoot-through period T_{sw} , as the diagram in Figure 5. In the following, the value of R_s can be calculated using equation (5).

$$R_s = \frac{2\Delta V_{sw_stress} T_{sw} (\Delta V_{sw_average} + \Delta V_{sw_spike})}{L_{lk} I_p^2} \quad (5)$$

Figure 5 - Characteristic waveforms considering the use of the RCD snubber

The capacitor C_s must be large enough to be able to store the energy coming from the leakage inductance L_{lk} that causes the voltage stress. Thus, adapting equation (5) together with equations (6), (7) and (8) gives equation (9), which allows the calculation of the minimum value for the capacitor C_s .

$$\varepsilon_{lk} = \frac{1}{2} L_{lk} I_p^2 f_{sw} \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_{s_max} = \varepsilon_{lk} \left(1 + \frac{\Delta V_{sw_average}}{\Delta V_{sw_stress}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$V_{Cs} = \Delta V_{sw_average} + \Delta V_{sw_stress} - V_{C1} \quad (7)$$

$$C_s = \frac{\epsilon_{s_max}}{V_{Cs}^2 f_{sw}} \quad (8)$$

It is important to point out that lower R_S resistance values result in lower voltage stresses and higher thermal dissipation, so the design should avoid high R_S values to lessen the impact on converter performance.

LCD Voltage Snubber

Among the non-dissipative passive damping circuits, the LCD topology stands out in applications because it possesses the robustness, simplicity, and low-cost characteristics characteristic of passive snubber while contributing to improved energy efficiency through the regeneration of part of the leakage energy absorbed during switching (Forouzesh, Abdelhakim, Siwakoti, & Blaabjerg, 2018).

The 1st stage of operation shown in Figure 6 (a) starts with the blocking of the S_W switch, leading to an increase of the voltage at points A-B. Consequently, the transfer of the leakage energy from the coupled inductors to capacitor C_s occurs. The stage ends when there is a current reversal in the coupled inductors I_{N1} and blocking of diode D_{S2} .

In the 2nd operating stage, most of the energy involved with the leakage has already been absorbed. Thus, the stage has a shorter duration period, as shown in Figure 7 (b). The voltage increase at terminal N_2 results in the blocking of D_{S1} , an event that delimits the end of the stage. The 3rd operating stage corresponds to the non-shoot-through period in which the snubber is not active.

The 4th operating stage shown in Figure 6 (d), corresponds to the shoot-through period, in which C_s and L_s go into resonance and the recovered energy is returned to the circuit, increasing the I_{SW} current. It is important to emphasize that the resonance period established by C_s and L_s is smaller than the shoot-through period, to allow the recovered energy to fully return to the converter circuit before the next cycle.

Figure 6 - Stages of operation of the LCD snubber.

The operation of the LCD snubber in the permanent regime assumes that there is a balance between the energy absorbed due to the voltage stress and the energy returned to the circuit input. The limits are defined by the capacity of C_s to store energy, and, by the capacity of the inductor L_s to return the received energy to the circuit. In this way, we can define that the effective capacity of the LCD snubber circuit to recover energy is proportional to the voltage variation over the capacitor C_s (Siwakoti, Loh, Blaabjerg, & Town, 2014). Furthermore, ideally, the energy recovered by the snubber should equal the total energy stored in the dispersion inductance. Therefore, equation (10) can be used to determine the minimum value of the capacitor C_s .

$$C_{s_min} = \frac{L_{lk}i_p^2}{(V_{sw_max}-V_{C1_average})^2} \quad (9)$$

Knowing the maximum value of current allowed on the Sw switch, it is possible to determine the minimum value of the inductor Ls using equation (11).

$$L_{s_min} = \frac{C_s(V_{sw_max}-V_{C1_average})^2}{(i_{sw_max}-i_{sw_average})^2} \quad (10)$$

Assuming that the resonance period of Ls and Cs must be less than or equal to the shoot-through period, the maximum value of the inductor Ls can be determined using equation (12).

$$L_{s_max} = \left(\frac{D_{st}}{f_{sw}\pi}\right)^2 \frac{1}{C_s} \quad (11)$$

Equations (10), (11), and (12) do not consider the losses inherent in the series resistances of the components. Thus, their use is limited in extreme scenarios where the losses in the components of the damping circuit are considerable.

Simulation Results

To evaluate the influence of the use of snubbers, and the effectiveness of the specification methodologies presented, computer simulations were performed using PSIM 2022 simulation software. Four cases were simulated, initially considering the converter operating without the use of the voltage snubber, and later with the use of RC, RCD, and LCD snubbers. The Quasi-Y converter parameters were kept the same in all simulations. Through the simulations, the performance data of the converter and the peak and average values of the voltage over the SW switch during the non-shoot-through period were collected.

Table 1 - Parameters of the Quasi-Y DC-DC converter used in the simulations.

Simulation Parameters	Values used
V _{in}	70 V _{DC}
L _{in}	3.4 mH
L _{lk}	30 μH
C ₁ ; C ₂ ; C _o	680 μF; 340μF; 0,25μF
R _{load} ; L _{load}	60 Ω; 0,5 mH
Duty Cycle	0,2222
Transform Ratio (N1:N2:N3)	99:99:33
Switching Frequency	5 kHz

Simulation of the Quasi-Y DC-DC converter without voltage snubber.

Figure 7 shows the voltage waveform over the SW switch, of the Quasi-Y DC-DC converter operating without a voltage snubber. The voltage stress on the switch is evident, followed by the resonance effect, during the non-shoot-through period. The efficiency of the converter under these conditions is 94.33%.

Figure 7 - Voltage on the SW switch of the Quasi-Y source DC-DC converter operating without a snubber.

Quasi-Y DC-DC converter simulation with RC snubber.

The methodology for specifying the RC snubber elements employs equations (1) and (2), the resonance frequency parameters f_R of 55 kHz, and the leakage inductance L_{lk} of 30 μ H. Resulting in the values of the resistance R_s of 10 Ω and the capacitor C_s of 0.28 μ F. Figure 8 shows the SW key voltage waveform.

Figure 8 - Voltage on SW switch of DC-DC converter Quasi-Y source operating with RC snubber.

The simulation analysis shows a considerable decrease of the resonant effect on the V_{SW} voltage and a 26.23% reduction of the voltage stress on the S_W switch if compared to the voltage stress without the use of voltage snubber, shown in Figure 7. Regarding the performance of the converter, there was a decrease of 16.18% compared to the converter without the snubber, a result consistent with the theoretical analysis.

Quasi-Y DC-DC converter simulation with RCD snubber.

The methodology for specifying the snubber components employs equations (5), (6), (7), (8), and (9) and the values in Table 2. Resulting in a resistance value R_s of 280 Ω and a capacitor value C_s of 1.35 μ F. The simulation of the schematic diagram in Figure 4, considering the calculated values for R_s and C_s , results in the waveforms shown in Figure 9.

Table 1 - RCD snubber calculation parameters.

Simulation Parameters	Values used
$\Delta V_{sw_average}$	170 V _{DC}
ΔV_{sw_stress}	170 V _{DC}
ΔV_{sw_spike}	550 V _{DC}
I_p	36 A
L_{lk}	30 μ H
f_{sw}	5 kHz

The simulation analysis shows that there was no decrease in the resonant effect on the V_{SW} voltage, however, the RCD snubber reduced the voltage stress from 550V to 340V, exactly the desired value during its sizing, representing a 38.18% reduction of the voltage stress on the S_W switch, if compared to the voltage stress without the use of voltage snubber, shown in Figure 7. There was a 16.22% reduction in the performance of the converter compared to the converter without snubber, a result consistent with the theoretical analysis.

Figure 9 - Voltage on SW switch of DC-DC converter Quasi-Y source operating with RCD snubber.

Quasi-Y DC-DC converter simulation with LCD snubber.

For the design of the elements that make up the LCD snubber, equations (10), (11), and (12) and the values in Table 3 were used. The calculations resulted in a minimum capacitor value C_s of $0.71 \mu\text{F}$ and minimum inductor values L_s of $19.72 \mu\text{H}$ and a maximum of $281 \mu\text{H}$. Simulation of the schematic diagram in Figure 7 with the calculated values for C_s and the maximum value of L_s resulted in the voltage waveform over the SW switch presented in Figure 10.

Table 2 - RCD snubber calculation parameters

Simulation Parameters	Values used
VC1_average	136,46 V
Vsw_max	370 V
Isw_average	5,81 A
Isw_max	50 A
L_{lk}	30 μH
Duty Cyclo	0,2222
fsw	5 kHz

Figure 10 - Voltage on SW switch of DC-DC converter Quasi-Y source operating with LCD snubber.

The simulation analysis shows that there was no decrease in the resonant effect at the V_{SW} voltage. However, the LCD snubber reduced the voltage stress from 550V to 383V, a percentage divergence of 3.4% from the specified voltage value of 370V. On the other hand, represents a 30.36% reduction in the voltage stress on the S_W switch compared to the voltage stress without the use of voltage snubber, shown in Figure 7. The data indicated that there was a 2.5% increase in the performance of the converter compared to the converter without the snubber.

The Table 4 presents the data from the four different simulations performed, allowing a quantitative evaluation of the application of the three types of damping circuits studied in the Quasi-Y source-type DC-DC converter.

Table 4 - Comparison of the operational effects considering the use of passive dampers.

Type of Snubber Circuit	Efficiency of Converter	Reduction of Voltage Surge (%)	Reduction of resonance in the converter
Without Snubber	94.33%	-reference-	--
RC	78.15%	26.23%	High
RCD	78.10%	38.18%	Low
LCD	96.85%	30.36%	Low

Conclusion

The operational behavior of the DC-DC converter Quasi-Y source related to voltage stresses in the switching processes represents a very detrimental aspect for the semiconductor switch, which together with the consequent resonance process, may make the commercial application inviable. Thus, the use of voltage snubbers in this class of converters can contribute to the solution of these limitations, making the application viable, and, allowing the use of components with lower voltage specifications, and improving the operational reliability issues. Among the types of snubbers evaluated in this work, the LCD type arrangement showed to be the most promising, as it presents a good capacity to attenuate voltage stresses while being able to contribute to the converter performance, not penalizing with losses but providing the recovery of part of the energy absorbed in the leakage inductances. In addition, this configuration uses only relatively low-cost passive components. However, during the development of the simulations, it was found that the use of the LCD snubber in the Quasi-Y source-type DC-DC

converter can interfere with the dynamic behavior of the converter, modifying the DC bus voltage values. Thus, further studies related to the interaction of the converter operation stages with those of the LCD snubber are required, to allow obtaining models that estimate more accurately the reflections and operational interactions between both.

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